

PEDAGOGICAL CONDITIONS OF FORMING VALUABLE ATTITUDE EXPERIENCE IN GENERAL SECONDARY EDUCATION STUDENTS

Akramova G.R.

p.f.d. (DSc), Professor

Khalilov Tahir Normurodovich

Asia International University Faculty of Social Sciences and Technology

Pedagogy and psychology

Master of the 2nd stage

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11207635>

Abstract: The time demands the ideological disarmament of the growing youth, which is the decisive force for ensuring the security of our country today and tomorrow, based on national values. To further increase the ideological immunity of students and young people in the fight against various foreign and harmful diseases, as well as in the formation of valuable experience. Ideas, their protection from various ideological and ideological threats, the formation of ideological immunity in society should lead to the education of a healthy, mature generation that deeply reflects the laws of development. Only then can we educate a spiritually mature person. raising a perfect generation - only spiritual people can create a great future.

Key words: value, custom, spirituality, enlightenment, education, upbringing, human heart, value, tradition, ritual, interactive, method, propaganda, technology.

Introduction:

Today, it is necessary to strengthen the stable ideological immunity of our youth against various foreign and harmful ideas and destructive ideas, to enrich their worldview, to form feelings of loyalty to the Motherland, to be involved in its development, to form national pride, to make them national and proud. It is important to educate in the spirit of pride and pride. it is important to prepare highly qualified specialists who can respond to universal human values, modern, sharp intellectual-spiritual competition, and make independent decisions. After all, in this era of global changes, continuous education is one of the important tasks facing the educational system. Therefore, we must educate new generations with a sense of national pride, which will give strength for our past and future, and strengthen our national statehood. Life experience proves that general secondary education is an important factor in forming the experience of valuable attitude in students.

Main part:

Today, it is necessary to arm students with healthy, humane ideas and national values and traditions that deeply reflect the laws of development in order to form the experience of a valuable attitude in students in general secondary schools. We can preserve and improve the national ideology only by carefully protecting our identity, morals, heritage, values, and national spirituality from the influence of harmful ideas and ideologies, and by forming ideological immunity in the hearts of our citizens and youth against them.

The system of values is inextricably linked with society, a natural organism that summarizes complex and multifaceted social relations, connections, and processes. The teacher's social point of view is formed and developed in the form of views, value system already during the general education school. Based on them, in the process of professional training, a valuable attitude towards the profession of pedagogy, the goals and means of pedagogical activity is formed. It is valuable for pedagogical activity attitude, in a broad sense, represents the orientation that forms the basis of the teacher's personality. Valuable directions of educational reforms are being decided in Uzbekistan as well. Article 41 of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan states that "Everyone has the right to education. Free general education is guaranteed by the state. School affairs are under the control of the state. In Article 42, "Everyone is guaranteed freedom of scientific and technical creativity, the right to use cultural achievements; "The state takes care of the cultural, scientific and technical development of the society". Article 4 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education" defines the right to education as a value as follows: "Gender, language, age, race, nationality, faith, religion , regardless of social origin, type of service, place of residence, how long they have lived in the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan, everyone is guaranteed equal rights to education". Effective ways to form a value system in students.

The process of training and education of personnel with positive qualities that can ensure the development of Uzbekistan and contribute to the rise to the level of advanced countries of the world. From this point of view, not only educational institutions, but also the family, neighborhood, and Youth Union form a social institution in educating the growing generation in the spirit of independence and loyalty to their values, patriotism and patriotism, respect for universal human values. In Uzbekistan, each of the public and non-governmental non-profit organizations has a special importance and influence.

The idea of today's era is the need to ideologically arm our youth, who are the decisive force for ensuring the security of our country today and tomorrow,

that is, to protect them from the influence of various foreign and harmful ideas and popular culture. It is demanding. If we say that this concept should be armed, not armed, then we will leave them alone and create conditions for them to master what seems "shiny" to their eyes. To get rid of the influence of ideas that are attractive on the surface, but in fact useless, that are slowly turning our pure-hearted youth into alien ideas by knowing their pure intentions. The only way is enlightenment. Therefore, we young people should not forget that we should "fight with thought against thought, idea against idea, and enlightenment against ignorance." Only then, the strength of ideological immunity in young people will be manifested in respect, faith and loyalty to national and universal values, cultural heritage, customs, traditions, language, history. Only then will it protect the nation from some threats associated with the globalization process.

The head of our state said from the pulpit of the 72nd session of the UN General Assembly, First of all, it is necessary to acquire the thinking of young people. Because most of the crimes related to extremist activity and violence are committed by young people under 30 years old. Shavkat Mirziyoev "The future of our planet, its well-being depends on what kind of people our children grow up to be." Representatives of the UN member states have agreed to develop the international convention "On the rights of youth" of Uzbekistan, to convey the true humanitarian nature of Islam to the world community, and to adopt a special resolution of the General Assembly called "Enlightenment and religious tolerance". The supported initiatives in Central Asia are one of the youngest regions, where 60% of the population is young people. All the people of the region realized that it can be solved only by expanding and strengthening cooperation.

This game is made in order to correctly analyze the value system. For this, the group is divided into two. The first group will be asked to state their wishes, and the second group will be asked to give a refusal answer. After ten minutes, the groups change their places. The following ideas can be used in the game:

- I still can't achieve my goal.
- No, don't say that. If you have a good intention and think good thoughts, it will definitely come true. I don't respect some of our teachers because their knowledge is shallow.
- No, it's not right to do that. Alisher Navoi said: "On the path of truth, teach someone a lesson with pain,
It's an irreplaceable good with a hundred treasures"

-I don't care, today I can be friends with another person, tomorrow with another person.

- It is a mistake to do so. Because a person who is a hypocrite in this world will have a hypocrite made of grass in the resurrection.

- I can always say what I want.

- You can do it, but it will always bring you trouble.

Because: "A black head has a red tongue, How many heads is he still eating" and others. After the game, the arguments used to reject the opinions, their reasons and content will be analyzed.

"Sense of dignity" training.

The goal of the training: to form students' self-expression, self-evaluation and feedback skills. Materials: whatman papers, markers. Course of training:

I. First, all students make a list of their special aspects on a piece of paper.

II. Then the trainer asks one of them to read a list of his special aspects.

III. After the student reads what is written in his list, the trainer asks other students to express their opinion about this student, that is, a feedback situation is created.

Students must comply with the following in the feedback process:

- 1) give feedback only when you are asked about a student;
- 2) while talking about your thoughts and feelings, mention the specific words and actions that caused them;
- 3) do not speak in a way that offends or offends others;
- 4) do not rate;
- 5) do not give advice: do not use sentences like "If I were in your place,...", "You should do ...".

It seems that the group that receives the most information from Internet sources are young men and women, and terrorist organizations use it as much as possible. He subjugates the thinking and mood of the active Internet audience to his ideas and sows the seeds of fear, hatred, and violence in the hearts of young people. In the context of globalization, the Internet has become the main tool for terrorists to identify new members, poison their brains and prepare them for their organization, collect and transfer funds, carry out terrorist activities and announce their goals. Current problems of preventing and combating violent extremism and terrorism require further improvement of political-legal, social and organizational-preventive means of protecting the young generation from the influence of destructive ideas, extremism and terrorism.

The history of the subject of values, its roots, and the formation of principles of human appreciation have a long history. In this regard, Western scientists mainly rely on the European cultural heritage and ideas, and mention the names of many scholars. The formation of the science of axiology (aksio - value, logos - teaching) in the West, which deals with values, is a certain basis for their views. We do not doubt that this topic, which Socrates and Plato, Aristotle and Hegel paid great attention to, has its own history in Western philosophy.

But this topic is not alien to the ancient and modern East, especially Uzbekistan! Searching for its deepest aspects not only from the West, but also from the East is probably not without benefits. There are traces of this topic in the works of thinkers such as Khorezmi, Farabi, al-Bukhari, al-Tirmizi, Beruni, Ibn Sina, Najmuddin Kubra, Yassavi, Naqshband, Ulug'bek, Navoi, Mashrab, Bedil, Behbudi, Avloni, whose names are forever etched in the history of our civilization. , deep edges are opened. It is a matter of finding these traces, not forgetting them, polishing them, and interpreting them objectively from the point of view of contemporary realities.

The history of the evaluation criteria created by our generations and ancestors goes back to the oldest tales, legends, stories, epics, i.e. examples of folk oral creativity. In the works about Spitamen, Muqanna and Jalaluddin Manguberdi, legends and epics about Alpomish, To'maris and Shiroq, many universal values are described, such as patriotism, sacrifice for the freedom of the people and the country. A bright example of our spiritual heritage is that "Avesta" is the holy book of Zoroastrianism, in which the value system of this religion, criteria of appreciation, national ideas of that time are vividly expressed.

In fact, all problems in society are solved based on the efforts of morally perfect people. Therefore, it is necessary to create effective means and methods of raising people's spirituality. Creating wide opportunities for young people to learn, as well as creating all the necessary conditions for the quality of education at the level of today's requirements, is one of the priorities of the reform of the education system in Uzbekistan. In the period of globalization and strengthening, economic, political, and spiritual changes in society create a unique phenomenon of synthesis in the worldview of our contemporaries. Having broad knowledge effectively influences the emergence of new ideas. Thinking can be mediated through the use of Internet, telephone, television and computer technologies. Because the content of a very large article or scientific work can be expressed in a half-page annotation, it means that even in a video

clip, the entire content of a person's life can be understood through a five-minute video.

Therefore, the development of technologies can have positive results on the one hand, and negative effects on the other. It is clear that depth of opportunity is needed for understanding. This does not mean developing critical thinking. In fact, developing critical thinking requires deep knowledge. "Today, in developed countries, the tendency of education to become a major branch of society is, on the one hand, the main productive force that brings a person to maturity, and on the other hand, it is a source of worldview formation and an indicator of its level. The impact of the civilization of the society is not the same, but the strength of the country depends on the effectiveness of the education system, which can form an idea about the level of enlightenment and the future of the society. Therefore, education is a component of spirituality. Because education serves not only the mastery of this or that science or field, but also the spiritual maturity of people. serves moral and spiritual growth. In this sense, just as there is no spirituality without education, there is no education without spirituality. They are closely related to each other and serve to improve the social life of the society.

Education is a field that serves to perfect the beautiful qualities of a person. People always need knowledge about humanity. In the concept of education, attention is paid to satisfying that inner need of a person, influencing his feelings, mind, and expanding his thinking. Active participation in socio-educational events allows for the growth of observation, creativity and creative self-expression in labor teams. The development of education is related to spirituality. It is an integral part of human life, the development of society cannot be imagined without it. Special attention was paid to education in the state policy of our republic, which is well aware that the education system is an important factor in raising human spirituality. Reforms in the field of education, which are continuing consistently in our country, serve to educate our youth as spiritual and well-rounded people. A broad way to build a humane and legal democratic state in our country, to form a civil society that embodies true patriotism, national and universal values and strictly adheres to them, and is able to harmonize its personal interests with the life of society. The interest of the country in order to open l. training of qualified people is being put on the agenda. It is necessary to create a system of effective ways, methods and effective means of educating a well-rounded person who has the ability to think, work and live independently, who can change his worldview and spirituality

based on the requirements of the times. In fact, "The spiritual and moral aspect of the education system is a component of the wider social environment, which is determined by the acquisition of moral and ethical laws and features by citizens and their compliance with the level of need." It is worth noting that only a person with a higher education, who has thoroughly mastered the laws of social life, has a rich spiritual world, and feels the essence of national values, can be economically free and become a support for democratic and fundamental reforms. In Eastern values, two things are highly praised: respect for the elder and honor for the younger. The environment will be healthy only if these two characteristics are the leading socio-spiritual principles. In addition to paying special attention to fundamental sciences, it is very important to increase the efficiency of spirituality in the process of struggle for the development of social and humanitarian sciences.

Summary

In the short time since we gained our independence, all necessary conditions have been created for the formation of a democratic, just and legal statehood, for the improvement of the well-being of our people, and for the restoration of its moral spirit. In particular, all the material and spiritual wealth left by our ancestors is being returned to our people, national traditions, traditions, and ancient values are being restored. The processes of realizing the identity of our nation are rapidly developing. All this has a positive effect on the increase of the prestige of our country at the international level and the restoration of the place of our nation in the world civilization. The ideology of national independence built on the basis of the traditions, customs, language and spirit of our people, which has been living for centuries, in harmony with universal values, conveys the feeling of confidence in the future to the hearts and minds of people, educates them in the spirit of love for the Motherland, humanity, honesty, serves to educate courage and patience, a sense of justice, and the pursuit of knowledge and enlightenment. In the process of education and upbringing of young people, the role of abilities is at a very high level. We can learn this during training sessions. The results of the training conducted among high school students show that the embodiment of the spirit of values is manifested in them in the form of concepts such as patriotism, devotion to duty, and humanitarianism. So, it is no exaggeration to say that we achieved the desired result from the training. As stated by the head of our state, Shavkat Mirziyoyev, "The law "On state policy regarding youth" was adopted in a new version in order to raise the work of educating the young generation in a healthy and well-rounded way to a new

level. Today, the world is discovering Uzbekistan through its national-cultural heritage, rich history, language, culture, customs and traditions, the integration of its values with universal ideas, and its achievements in the field of art and architecture, science and culture. Therefore, we can become active promoters and not passive receivers in the process of globalization

List of references:

1. Tashmetov, T. Kh. (2020). Modern methods of inculcating the national idea in the minds of young people.
2. Mirziyoev Sh.M. We will resolutely continue our path of national development and raise it to a new level. Volume 1. - Tashkent: Uzbekistan, 2017. - B.
3. Shermukhamedova N. Education is the priority direction of socialization. Proceedings of the scientific-practical conference. - Tashkent: "Nishon" publishing house, 2010. - p. 24.
4. Strong ideological immunity plays an important role in protecting young people from foreign ideas. Strong ideological immunity plays an important role in protecting young people against ideas.
5. Турдиев, Б. (2024). JAMIYAT IDEOSFERASINING IJTIMOYIY-FALSAFIY TAHLILI. Ижтимоий-гуманитар фанларнинг долзарб муаммолари/Актуальные проблемы социально-гуманитарных наук/Actual Problems of Humanities and Social Sciences., 4(2).
6. Sobirovich, T. B. (2023). Basic Criteria for Building the Third Renaissance in Uzbekistan. Asian Journal of Applied Science and Technology (AJAST), 7(1), 149-157.
7. Sobirovich, T. B. (2023). MANIFESTATION OF CIVIL SOCIETY IN THE IDEOSPHERE OF UZBEKISTAN. Innovative Society: Problems, Analysis and Development Prospects, 89-92.
8. Sobirovich, T. B., & Norman, Z. D. M. (2023). Harmony of National and Universal Values in Uzbekistan. Harmony, 7(1), 08-16.
9. Turdiyev B. S. The role of national harmony in the strategy of spiritual renewal //Scientific Bulletin of Namangan State University. – 2019. – T. 1. – №. 6. – С. 229-233.